

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYTOPREPARATIONS BASED ON *STELLARIA MEDIA* (L.) VILL.

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Relevance. Chickweed (*Stellaria media* (L.) Vill.) is a widely distributed medicinal plant containing flavonoids (apigenin and kaempferol glycosides), phenolic acids, and saponins, exhibiting antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activity. The plant is used in traditional medicine for inflammatory diseases and metabolic disorders, which confirms the prospects for the development of phytopreparations.

Aim of the study. To summarize current data on the phytochemical composition and pharmacological properties of *S. media* and to assess the possibilities of its application in pharmaceutical practice.

Materials and methods. A review of publications in *PubMed*, *Scopus*, and *Web of Science* databases for 2000-2025 was carried out; data on chemical composition, pharmacological effects, and extraction methods were analyzed.

Results. More than 12 flavonoids, mainly apigenin C-glycosides, as well as saponins and phenolic acids, have been identified in *S. media* extracts, which determine its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential. The extracts demonstrate pronounced radical scavenging activity, moderate inhibition of lipoxygenase and hyaluronidase, accelerate wound healing in cell models, and show antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Several studies have shown antiviral activity of aqueous and alcoholic fractions against HBV. Anti-obesity effects have also been reported in experimental animal studies.

Conclusion. The body of evidence indicates the prospects for developing phytopreparations based on chickweed, primarily topical formulations for the treatment of inflammatory and infectious skin diseases. Further standardization by flavonoid content and preclinical and clinical studies on safety and efficacy are required.